

Zymograms of (a) malate dehydrogenase, (b) phosphoglucose isomerase, (c) isocitrate dehydrogenase, (d) esterase, (e) catalase, and (f) malic enzyme.

PMS, 10 mg NBT, 10 mg NAD, 10 ml malate (0.05M, pH 6) in 40 ml 0.05M tris-HCl buffer, pH 8.5, incubate gel in the dark for 15 min at 40°C. *Peroxidase (Pox)*: 15 μ l H₂O₂ solution (30%), 1 ml CaCl₂ solution (0.1M), 2.5 ml N,N'-dimethyl formamide, 20 mg 3-amino-9-ethyl carbazole in 42 ml acetate buffer (0.05M, pH 5). *6-Phosphoglucuronate dehydrogenase (Pgd)*: 10 mg sodium phosphoglucuronate, 5 mg NADP, 10 mg NBT, 1 mg PMS, 2 ml MgCl₂ (0.1M) in 50 ml 0.05M tris-HCl buffer, pH 8.5, incubate gel in the dark for 15 min at 40°C. *Phosphoglucose isomerase (Pgi)*: 50 mg fructose-6-phosphate, 5 mg NADP, 10 mg NBT, 1 mg PMS, 2 ml MgCl₂ (0.1M), 3 μ l glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase in 20 ml tris-HCl buffer (0.5M, pH 8.5). Mix with 25 ml 2% agar

solution kept at 55°C and pour on the slice. Incubate in the dark for 15 min at 40°C. *Shikimate dehydrogenase (Sdh)*: 25 mg shikimic acid, 5 mg NADP, 10 mg NBT, 1 mg PMS in 50 ml 0.05M tris-HCl buffer, pH 8.5, incubate gel in the dark for 15 min at 40°C. *Superoxide dismutase (Sod)*: 15 mg NBT, 3 mg riboflavin, 4 mg EDTA, in 0.05M tris-HCl buffer, pH 8.5, incubate at 37°C in dark for 30 min, then expose to UV light. *Tetrazolium oxidase (To)*: 25 mg NAD, 20 mg NBT, 5 mg PMS, in 50 ml 0.05M tris-HCl, pH 8.5. Expose gel to light until white bands appear on blue background.

Using this technique, we investigated a total of 18 enzymes (see table). The figure shows the zymogram pattern of the 6 of 11 enzymes for which activity was noted. □

Cytogenetics of the whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* (Horváth)

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Cellular and karyotypic attributes such as chromosome number, morphology, morphometrics, and behavior involving position of chromosomes at various phases of cell division, differential contraction, bivalent configuration, etc., are important in understanding insect species relationships. We investigated the cytogenetics of WBPH. Oocytes and spermatocytes of insectary-reared, newly emerged adults were examined using the standard squash technique and lacto-aceto-orcein staining method.

Reproductive cells simultaneously underwent both the conventional meiotic sequence and reverse meiosis, which led to the occurrence of uninucleated and binucleated meiocytes (Fig. 1). Binucleated cells resulted from failures of the tetrads of meiotic inversions to undergo complete cytokinesis. The frequency of

occurrence of binucleated cells in 15 males that were examined was 21 per individual, or about 24% of the average total (88) meiocytes detected. Uninucleated cells averaged about 50 per insect or almost 56% of the total dividing cells.

The uninucleated interphase cells were 47 μ long and 30 μ wide; the binucleated cells were 36 μ long and 19 μ wide. The nuclei of uninucleated cells were 5-10 μ long and 8-9 μ wide; the circular nuclei of binucleated cells had a 5 μ diameter. Of the two nuclei in binucleated cells, only one survived and proceeded to the reductional division of meiosis. The other nucleus degenerated rapidly and was lost before metaphase I.

The mean number of dividing and nondividing testicular cells observed per individual was 88 and 94, giving a meiotic index of about 50%. Sperm length was 12 to 30 μ .

WBPH chromosomes were holocentric. The kinetochores were diffused along the entire length of both autosomes and sex chromosomes. The diploid number was 2n=29, and 2n=30 in females. The sex chromosome in each testicular cell was a univalent X body, 2 μ long and 1 to 1.5 μ wide. The oogonial cells had XX bivalents,

1. Uninucleated (top) and binucleated (bottom) meiocytes (1000X) of *S. furcifera*

2. Complete genome in male *S. furcifera* (2n = 14II A + X). Sex chromosome is indicated by an arrow.

each about 3 μ long. The sex-determining mechanism was XX-XO type, the male being heterogametic and the female

homogametic. Thus, the complete genome in males comprised 14 bivalent autosomes plus an X chromosome

(Fig. 2), whereas females had 14 bivalent autosomes plus XX sex chromosomes. □

A *Leersia*-feeding brown planthopper (BPH) biotype in North Sumatra, Indonesia

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We found a large BPH population of macropterous and brachypterous adults and nymphs at various instars inhabiting *Leersia hexandra* in a fallow rice field at Petapahan, Lubuk Pakam, Deli Serdang, North Sumatra, in Sep 1983. Except for significantly smaller body size, morphological characters of BPH specimens collected on *L. hexandra* and on IR42 and Pelita I/1 at the same location were identical (Fig. 1).

Preliminary experiments compared the reactions of *Leersia*-BPH to host plants with the reaction of BPH biotype 3 which infests rice in North Sumatra. In a host preference test in a cage with *L. hexandra* and susceptible Pelita I/1, adult females of *Leersia*-BPH all settled on *L. hexandra* within 1 d, while biotype 3 females rejected it. Adult females of *Leersia*-BPH survived only a few days and reproduced little progeny on Pelita I/1. They survived

1. Paramere of the *Leersia*-BPH(upper) and rice feeding BPH, biotype 3 (lower).

normally and reproduced readily on *L. hexandra*. One *Leersia*-BPH female allowed to oviposit on *L. hexandra* for 1 wk produced about 120 nymphs. When the first-instar nymphs were

2. Survival trends of *Leersia*-BPH and biotype 3 nymphs on detached *L. hexandra*.

reared on detached stems of *L. hexandra* in test tubes, 93-100% of nymphs emerged to adults within 2 wk. First-instar biotype 3 nymphs died (Fig. 2). Female *Leersia*-BPH excreted little honeydew on Pelita I/1 and IR42 (2-4 mg/female daily). Biotype 3 females excreted 30-40 mg honeydew/female daily.

These results indicate that the *Leersia*-BPH is a distinct host-determined BPH biotype. □

Hot water treatment to remove insects from rice plants used in the plant-hopper and leafhopper rearing program

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In the IRRI GEU program, thousands of rice plants are grown each month as food for the hopper rearing program. Because greenhouse space is limited they must be grown outdoors, where they are often infested with eggs of the various hopper species and predators. This contamination leads to

mixing of hopper biotypes and brings unwanted predators into the rearing cages. To eliminate those insects, plants are sprayed with water and placed in cages. Hatching nymphs are removed after 11 d. This is time-consuming and requires greenhouse space.

We evaluated hot water treatment for control of brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens*, whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera*, green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens*, and the predatory mirid bug *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis*.

Gravid females of BPH, WBPH, GLH, and *Cyrtorhinus* were separately

Egg mortality caused by dipping rice plants in 44°C hot water for 30 min. Bars with different letters differ significantly at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.